

yellowing virus. This is the first report of the occurrence of this disease in the tropics. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from stubbles of different rice varieties 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after harvest. West Bengal, India, 1978.

Variety	Transmission (%) in seedlings			
	30 days	60 days	90 days	120 days
Ratna	10	0	0	0
Pankaj	10	5	0	0
Cauvery	0	0	0	0
IET1441	0	0	0	0
IR579	20	10	0	0
IET2295	0	0	0	0
IET2914	30	20	10	0
Jaya	20	10	0	0
IR8	10	0	0	0
Laghu	20	10	0	0
Kathamuk	20	10	0	0
Rajmalati	20	5	0	0
Kalamkathi	10	0	0	0
Lakhansail	20	10	0	0
Sachimohan	20	10	0	0
Jhulur	10	0	0	0
Dhushri	20	10	0	0
Dudhshar	10	0	0	0
Ashanlaya	20	10	0	0
Madhumalati	20	10	0	0

Indrak 7/20/80
Further studies on the potential of rice stubble for spreading tungro in West Bengal, India

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A previous study on the potential of rice stubble in spreading tungro in West Bengal confirmed that infected stubbles of TN1 plants can act as a virus source and maintain the virus for 75 days. The same procedure was used to test the infected stubbles of high yielding and local varieties for efficiency in transmitting virus.

Of the nine high yielding varieties (Ratna, Pankaj, Cauvery, IET1441, IR579, IET2295, IET2914, Jaya, and IR8) and 11 local varieties (Laghu, Kathamuk, Rajmalati, Kalamkathi, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Jhulur, Dhushri, Dudhshar, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati) tested (see table), Ratna and IR8

retained the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days; Pankaj, IR579, and Jaya for 60 days; and IET2914 for 90 days. The stubbles of Cauvery, IET1441, and IET2295 carried no virus.

Of the local varieties tested, Kalamkathi and Dudhshar carried the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days;

the stubbles of Laghu, Rajmalati, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati retained the virus for 60 days; and those of Kathamuk and Dhushri for 90 days (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Effect of transplanting date and seedling age at transplanting on spread of tungro

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Experiments were conducted at the plant virus experimental field to determine the effect of transplanting date and of

seedling age at transplanting on the spread of tungro virus disease in a rice crop during 1978 kharif. The Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, funded the research.

In the first experiment 25-day-old TN1 seedlings were transplanted at 5-day intervals in 3-m² replicated plots provided with uniform inoculum for tungro virus (1 infected plant/plot). The

number of plants with tungro symptoms was recorded at 3- to 6-day intervals until the end of September.

Transplanting date had pronounced effects on the spread of tungro (see table). The spread of the disease increased when the transplanting date gradually shifted from mid-July to the first week of August, when spread became maximum. With subsequent shifts of

Effect of transplanting date and age at transplanting of TN1 seedlings on the spread of rice tungro virus (RTV) disease during 1978 kharif (Jul–Nov) and the corresponding vector population in the field, West Bengal, India.

Date of observation	LH ^a (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)
	A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N	
28 Jul	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—						
2 Aug	1	0	—	1	0	—	2	0	—						
7 Aug	0	2	—	4	2	—	3	9	—	3	5	—			
12 Aug	1	1	—	1	37	—	3	70	—	2	38	—	4	11	—
17 Aug	1	0	—	0	15	—	0	20	—	0	40	—	0	43	—

Effect of transplanting date of 25-day-old TN1 seedlings

(Continued on next page)

Effect of transplanting date cont'd.

Date of observation	LH ^a (no.)			RTV infection			LH (no.)			RTV infection			LH (no.)			RTV infection			LH (no.)			RTV infection														
	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)	A	N	(%)												
Effect of transplanting date of 25-day-old TN1 seedlings																																				
	16 Jul						21 Jul						26 Jul						1 Aug						6 Aug						11 Aug					
22 Aug	0	0	2.77	1	2	—	1	3	—	1	14	—	2	29	—	2	35	—																		
27 Aug	1	0	2.77	2	23	5.55	2	28	5.55	7	39	2.77	4	47	2.77	4	18	—																		
4 Sep	1	1	5.55	10	14	5.55	15	33	9.72	16	31	9.72	8	42	5.55	11	43	—																		
11 Sep	0	4	5.55	6	6	9.72	3	2	15.27	10	8	20.83	21	13	8.33	22	16	2.77																		
16 Sep	2	0	5.55	7	0	9.72	11	12	15.27	20	12	20.83	24	12	8.33	21	15	2.77																		
19 Sep	2	0	5.55	4	4	9.72	10	4	15.27	13	5	41.66	30	15	11.11	42	28	4.16																		
23 Sep	0	0	5.55	1	2	9.72	15	12	15.27	25	18	41.66	33	43	11.11	56	46	4.16																		
25 Sep	2	0	5.55	24	1	9.72	24	25	15.27	64	35	41.66	56	46	11.11	44	66	4.16																		

Effect of seedling age at transplanting

	55 days old			50 days old			45 days old			40 days old			35 days old		
12 Aug	0	0	—	5	0	—	6	0	—	2	0	—	0	0	—
17 Aug	7	16	—	6	13	—	3	15	—	1	10	—	1	4	—
19 Aug	3	18	—	4	41	—	6	63	—	16	55	—	0	22	—
21 Aug	2	10	—	3	20	—	2	16	—	2	25	—	2	23	—
26 Aug	2	16	4.16	6	15	5.55	3	22	—	3	14	—	2	13	—
2 Sep	1	10	6.94	5	37	9.72	4	40	6.94	5	14	6.94	5	13	5.55
4 Sep	7	39	6.94	9	35	9.72	4	40	6.94	5	14	6.94	5	13	5.55
11 Sep	4	5	6.94	9	35	9.72	13	40	13.88	6	36	6.94	6	25	5.55
16 Sep	15	16	6.94	23	18	9.72	24	8	20.83	16	6	34.72	16	6	12.50
19 Sep	21	10	6.94	11	11	9.72	14	8	20.83	15	0	41.66	11	7	12.50
23 Sep	5	4	6.94	35	11	9.72	60	30	20.83	16	4	41.66	29	14	12.50
25 Sep	34	31	6.94	26	45	9.72	32	38	20.83	26	20	41.66	44	72	12.50

^aLH = leafhoppers; A = adults; N = nymphs.

transplanting time toward mid-August, however, the spread gradually decreased.

In the second experiment, TN1 seedlings — 35, 40, 45, 50, and 55 days old — were transplanted on 1 August

1978 in 3-m² replicated plots. The number of plants with tungro symptoms was recorded at 2- to 5-day intervals until the end of September.

Age at transplanting had marked

effects on tungro spread during kharif (see table). Disease spread was maximum in seedlings transplanted at 40 days old. The extent of infection was lower in seedlings transplanted earlier or later. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice gall midge outbreaks in Thailand

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has long been a major pest of rainfed rice in Thailand. Annual infestations in northern, northeastern, and eastern Thailand are heavy. In recent years, severe outbreaks have also occurred on irrigated dry-season rice in the central plain. Gall midge distribution has now extended to the southern peninsula.

Table 1. Occurrence of the rice gall midge at various locations in Thailand, 6–18 September 1979 (wet season).

Location	Damaged tillers (%)	Rice variety affected
Lam-Ngob, Trad	11.7	No. 28 (local variety)
Ban Ta Kak, Trad	19.4	RD1
Bau, Chantaburi	12.3	Paung-Ngen
Ban Don Chik, Ubonratchatani	26.5	Niew-San-Pa-Tong
Ban Pa Rauk, Chiangrai	40.1	Niew-San-Pa-Tong

Areas where gall midge is endemic were surveyed in the 1979 wet season. Heavily infested areas were observed at the insects' population peak in September. Healthy tillers and galls were recorded on 100–200 randomly selected hills at each site. Unemerged galls were also randomly

collected and dissected to determine parasitism incidence.

Gall midge infestation was highest (40% damaged tillers) on Niew-San-Pa-Tong rice at Ban Pa Rauk, Chiangrai province, northern Thailand (Table 1). At Ubonratchatani in the northeast,